

The Distributional Effect of Trade on the CEO Market*

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Abstract

We study the relationship between trade openness and CEO pay dispersion across firms. Using US firm-level data, we show that trade raises CEO equilibrium pay in the most productive firms but reduces it in the least productive ones. An increase of 10% in the industry openness degree raises CEO compensation by about 35% and 20% in firms at the 99th and 95th percentiles of the productivity distribution, respectively. However, CEO compensation falls by 7% in firms at the 20th percentile. Our results show that trade openness impacts inequality within the very top of the income distribution, where skill differentials are less evident.

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1 Introduction

The post-1970 era of trade integration coincided with a rapid rise of inequality at the top of the income distribution (Piketty and Saez, 2003; Atkinson et al., 2011; Gabaix et al., 2016).¹ This period also coincided with an increase in the dispersion of chief executive officer (CEO) pay. For instance, Frydman and Saks (2010) show that the dispersion of earnings across executives remained fairly constant for several decades after WWII and then began to fan out after the 1970s.² CEOs are very representative at the top of the earnings distribution (Bakija et al., 2008; Kaplan and Rauh, 2013).³ Thus, understanding the drivers of CEO pay dispersion can shed light into the forces behind the rise in top income inequality. In this paper, we study the relationship between trade openness and CEO pay dispersion.

We show that trade openness triggers distributional effects in the market for CEOs. Specifically, we find that trade integration raises CEO equilibrium pay in the most productive firms but reduces it in the least productive ones. That is, trade pushes the super-rich ahead relative to the rich. Hence, our results show that trade not only impacts inequality between broadly defined groups, which has been the main focus of the trade-inequality literature so far (Harrison et al., 2010), but also inequality within the very top of the income distribution, where skill differentials are less evident.⁴ Thus, our findings suggest a potential connection between trade openness and the movement in top income inequality: the distributional effect of trade on the CEO market.

To study the relationship between trade openness and CEO pay dispersion, we proceed in three steps. We start by documenting some facts that motivate our study. Concretely, we document (i) the country-level relationship between trade openness and inequality at the very top of the income distribution, (ii) the coincidental rising trends exhibited by trade openness and

¹Gabaix et al. (2016) document that both the income share of the top 0.1% relative to that of the top 1%, and the income share of the top 1% relative to that of the top 10% exhibit an upward trend since the late 1970s. Atkinson et al. (2011) and Saez (2017) show that non-capital income inequality is a significant driver of the rise in top income inequality.

²Frydman and Saks (2010) show that the ratio of pay at the 90th to the 25th percentiles fell from 3.4 to 2.8 from 1936 to 1970, whereas it rose from 3 to 7.7 during the 1970-2005 period.

³Bakija et al. (2008) document that executives, managers and supervisors in the non-finance sector account for approximately 40% of those in the top 0.1% in terms of income in the 1979-2005 period, and approximately one-third of the top 1%.

⁴As argued by Gabaix and Landier (2008), the distribution of CEO talent appears to be extremely small at the top; indeed, the authors rank CEOs by talent and replace CEO number 250 by the number one CEO and show that the value of her/his firm will increase by only 0.0016%.

the dispersion of CEO pay in the US economy during the past decades, and (iii) US firm-level correlations between productivity, export orientation, revenues, and executive compensation.

In the second step, in the spirit of Monte (2011), we develop a general equilibrium open-economy model of heterogeneous firms and heterogeneous CEO talent, which we use to frame our empirical analysis. We derive an equilibrium earnings equation that relates trade openness and CEO pay across firms that exhibit different levels of total factor productivity. Then, we use the earnings equation to simulate the distributional effect of trade openness on the CEO market in a given industry. Our policy experiment entails a fall in the cost of serving existing foreign markets. The model shows that industry trade openness induces a reallocation of revenues across firms, which together with rent sharing within firms, imply that CEO equilibrium pay falls in the least productive firms but rises in the most productive ones.

In the third step, we test the main predictions of the model. To do so, we assemble panel data of 1,085 US companies spanning the period 1992-2017, using data collected from *Compustat*. Our empirical design relies on panel model regressions. We measure CEO compensation as in Gabaix and Landier (2008). We build a firm-level total factor productivity measure by using Levinsohn and Petrin's (2003) approach. In addition, we build an industry-level trade intensity variable proxied by the weighted average of the firm-level ratio of export sales to total sales.

Our baseline empirical model regresses firm CEO compensation against time and industry fixed effects, firm total factor productivity, the degree of openness in the industry where a firm produces, and the interaction between the latter two variables. We include different sets of covariates aimed at controlling for potential confounding explanations for the rise of CEO pay dispersion within industries. Concretely, we include variables that control for CEO characteristics, the quality of the firm's corporate governance, the firm's organizational knowledge, and firm size. To control for potential endogeneity, we use tariffs as instrumental variables.

We find a negative and statistically significant effect of industry openness on the firm's CEO pay. In addition, we find a positive and statistically significant interaction effect between industry openness and the firm's total factor productivity. The overall effect of industry openness on CEO compensation is positive for the most productive firms, whereas it is negative for the least productive firms. Concretely, an increase of 10% in the industry openness degree

raises CEO compensation by about 35% and 20% in firms at the 99th and 95th percentiles of the productivity distribution, respectively. However, CEO compensation falls by 7% in firms at the 20th percentile. Thus, trade exposure raises CEO pay dispersion within industries, having a positive effect on CEO compensation in the most productive firms but a negative effect in the least productive firms. The aggregate elasticity implied by our estimates is about 0.1; that is, an increase of 10% in trade openness raises aggregate CEO compensation by 1%. We also study the within-sample explanatory power of trade openness on CEO pay that is implied by the marginal effects we found. We get that trade openness explains 34%, 20%, and 47% of the observed change in CEO pay during the period 1992-2017 in firms at the 99th, 95th, and 20th percentiles of the productivity distribution, respectively.

We conclude this paper by discussing how the distributional effect of trade on the CEO market may impact the top of the income distribution. To do so, we derive an equation that relates the marginal effect of trade openness on CEO compensation and the aggregate impact of trade on inequality at the top of the income distribution. We also illustrate how the equation can be used to quantify the fraction of the overall effect of trade on inequality at the top of the distribution that is accounted for by the distributional effects in the CEO market.

The seminal literature on CEO pay focused on closed-economy frameworks (Garicano and Rossi-Hansberg, 2006; Gabaix and Landier, 2008; Bertrand and Mullainathan, 2001; among others).⁵ Verhoogen (2008) studies the effect of trade on wage inequality in the Mexican manufacturing sector.⁶ Along with our paper, there are two articles that look at the CEO market in open-economy environments. Ma and Ruzic (2020) study the effect of globalization on inequality within firms, specifically, on the CEO-to-worker pay ratio. Thus, the authors examine how globalization shapes the income gap between the very rich and the rest of the population. Instead, our analysis studies the effect of trade integration on CEO pay dispersion between firms. Therefore, our paper responds to the question of why the super-rich have pulled ahead relative to the rich in the US economy during the past decades. Keller and Olney (2017) use reduced-form regressions to study the effects of globalization on the level of

⁵Frydman and Papanikolaou (2018) develop a general equilibrium model that generates predictions about executive pay inequality across firms. They consider a closed-economy model, which thus discards, by design, the role of trade openness as a determinant of pay inequality among executives.

⁶Different from the CEO pay literature, Verhoogen (2008) analyzes wage inequality between white-collar and blue-collar workers. The channel highlighted by Verhoogen (2008) is the effect of trade on the quality of the goods produced by the more productive plant relative to those produced by the less productive plants.

executive compensation. Different from Keller and Olney (2017), we show that the impact of trade integration on CEO equilibrium pay is heterogeneous across firms. Concretely, our results highlight that trade openness raises CEO pay in the most productive firms but reduces it in the least productive ones. Thus, we show that trade impacts inequality within the very top of the income distribution.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 documents some macro-level and micro-level stylized facts. Section 3 develops the model. Section 4 describes the data. Section 5 discusses our empirical approach. Section 6 presents and discusses our results. Section 7 concludes this paper.

2 Motivating facts

In this section we present some facts that motivate our analysis. We first use macro data to document a positive relationship between trade openness and inequality within the top of the income distribution. Then, we show the coincidental rising trend exhibited by trade openness and the dispersion of US executive compensation in recent decades. Lastly, we report US firm-level correlations between (i) the firm's export orientation and the firm's productivity, (ii) the firm's revenues and the firm's productivity, and (iii) CEO compensation and the firm's productivity. We also discuss how these facts motivate different pieces of our analysis.

Trade openness and top income inequality

We first motivate a positive relation between trade openness and top income inequality. We build an unbalanced panel data of 59 countries spanning the period 1975-2018.⁷ We measure top income inequality as the income share of the richest $i\%$ relative to the income share of the richest $j\%$ of the population, $z^{i/j}$. Our data for the top income shares were collected from the *World Wealth and Income Data* (WID).⁸ We extract the covariates from the *World*

⁷We excluded countries with a GDP per capita lower than US\$ 10,000 (measured in real purchasing power parity).

⁸The income variable is the pre-tax personal income flows accrued by the owners of the production factors, labor, and capital, before taking into account the pension system.

Development Indicators of the World Bank (WDI). We estimate the following empirical model:

$$\ln \tilde{z}_{it} = \beta_1 \ln O_{it} + X_{it}\beta_2 + \psi_i + \varepsilon_{it}. \quad (\text{S1})$$

for $\tilde{z} \in \{z^{0.001/0.01}, z^{0.001/0.1}, z^{0.001/1}\}$, where O_{it} is the sum of exports plus imports as a fraction of GDP, X_{it} is public spending normalized by GDP, ψ_i are country fixed effects, and ε_{it} is an i.i.d. error term.

Table 1 presents the results. The country-level estimates suggest a positive relation between trade openness and inequality within the top of the income distribution. Our paper studies a potential driver of the latter relationship: the distributional effect of trade on the CEO market.

Trade openness and the dispersion of CEO pay

Three coincidental facts have been well documented in the literature: the fast pace of trade integration followed by the US economy starting in the mid-1970s,⁹ the rapid rise in top income inequality in the US economy since the beginning of the 1980s (Piketty and Saez, 2003; Atkinson et al., 2011; Gabaix et al., 2016), and the rise in executive compensation during the 1980s and 1990s (Gabaix and Landier, 2008; Frydman and Saks, 2010; Edmans et al., 2017).¹⁰ We next document a fourth coincidental fact: an increasing dispersion of pay across executives starting in the 1970s.

Fig. 1 shows the ratio of executive pay at the 90th to the 25th percentiles in the United States during the past decades (Frydman and Saks, 2010).¹¹ We observe that the dispersion of pay across executives slightly fell until the late 1960s (from 3.4 to 2.8). In contrast, this ratio rose from 3 to 7.7 during the 1970-2005 period. This evidence suggests that trade openness not only impacted the level of CEO pay (Keller and Olney, 2017) or the CEO-to-worker pay ratio within a firm (Ma and Ruzic, 2020), but could have also triggered distributional effects in the

⁹See the *World Development Indicators* of the World Bank.

¹⁰Motivated by these stylized facts, Ma and Ruzic (2020) and Keller and Olney (2017) suggest that trade integration is an important force behind the CEO-to-worker pay ratio within a firm and the level of executive compensation, respectively.

¹¹Total compensation is the sum of salaries, bonuses, long-term bonus payments, and the Black-Scholes value of stock option grants. See Frydman and Saks (2010) for further details on the construction of the executive pay variable.

market of CEOs. The increasing dispersion in CEO pay exhibited in Fig. 1 and its relationship with trade integration is the central focus of our analysis.

Export orientation, revenues, CEO pay, and productivity

Our third set of motivating facts considers US firm-level correlations between (i) the firm’s export orientation and the firm’s productivity, (ii) the firm’s revenues and the firm’s productivity, and (iii) CEO compensation and the firm’s productivity.¹²

Table 2 presents the results of correlations (i) to (iii). We observe that, within an industry, more productive firms are more export oriented, generate greater revenues, and pay higher CEO compensation. In the next section, we present a framework that generates the facts exhibited in Table 2. The model will motivate the empirical analysis we perform in Section 5.

3 The model

In the spirit of Monte (2011), we develop a general equilibrium open-economy model with heterogeneous firms and heterogeneous CEO talent. We use this model to motivate the empirical analysis of Section 5. We first derive an equilibrium earnings equation that relates trade openness, firm productivity, and CEO earnings. Then, we use the earnings equation to simulate the distributional effect of trade openness on the CEO market. To ease exposure, the derivation of the main equations of the model are provided in the appendices.

3.1 Preferences and production

Consumer preferences are defined over consumption of a continuum of horizontally-differentiated varieties and take the form as in Dixit and Stiglitz (1977):

$$U = \left[\int_{\psi \in \Psi} q(\psi)^{\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}} d\psi \right]^{\frac{\sigma}{\sigma-1}}, \quad (1)$$

¹²We proxy the export orientation of a firm by the ratio of export sales to total sales. Firm’s productivity refers to the firm’s total factor productivity, which is built by using Levinsohn and Petrin’s (2003) approach. We measure CEO compensation following Gabaix and Landier (2008); that is, we sum salary, bonuses, the total value of restricted stocks granted, the Black-Scholes total value of stock options granted, and long-term incentive payouts. We postpone the detailed description of the data to Section 4.

where the measure of set Ψ represents the mass of available goods, and $\sigma > 1$ is the elasticity of substitution between any two goods.¹³

A continuum of firms choose to produce a different variety. Firms are heterogeneous regarding their total factor productivity, a . The firm's productivity parameter a is revealed only after incurring an irreversible investment $e \in \mathbb{R}_+$, which is measured in units of production labor. If a firm decides to produce, it faces an exogenous probability ζ of being shocked by an event that forces it to exit. Exporting firms face two additional costs: a per-unit trade cost $\tau > 1$, and a fixed export entry cost $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}_+$ (measured in units of production labor). As in Melitz (2003), the sunk export entry cost is incurred after the productivity level of the firm is unveiled. The domestic economy trades with a single identical foreign economy.

There is also a continuum of individuals, who must decide whether to be a CEO or a production worker. Agents have heterogeneous talent x to run a firm, but they are identical as production workers. Once a firm draws its initial productivity parameter, CEOs are hired in a competitive market for talent. Then, production is carried out by a firm, a CEO, and production workers. The production of each variety involves a fixed production cost $f \in \mathbb{R}_+$, measured in units of production labor, and a constant marginal cost that depends on CEO talent and the firm's productivity, $c(x, a) : (1, \infty) \times (1, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$, which strictly decreases in each argument individually.

3.2 The equilibrium earnings equation

We define the surplus of a firm as the difference between its revenues and the total cost of production labor. The surplus of a type- a firm, with export status d , that is managed by a type- x CEO, can be expressed as:¹⁴

$$s(x, a, d) = (1 + d\tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{r(x, a, 0)}{\sigma} - v(f + d\kappa), \quad (2)$$

where $d = 1(d = 0)$ for an exporting (non-exporting) firm, v is the wage paid for production labor, and $r(x, a, 0)$ are the revenues earned from domestic sales or *domestic revenues*, which

¹³Appendix A formally presents the consumer's maximization problem.

¹⁴The derivation of the surplus equation is provided in Appendix A.

are equal to

$$r(x, a, 0) = R \left[\frac{v}{P \left(\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma} \right)} \right]^{1-\sigma} c(x, a)^{1-\sigma}, \quad (3)$$

where R denotes aggregate expenditure, and P is an index of all the varieties' prices.

Eq. (2) shows that a firm's surplus depends positively on its domestic revenues. Exporting firms produce additional revenues from serving foreign markets and, thus, accrue a greater surplus than identical firms that only serve the local market. The revenues earned from export sales depend positively on the degree of openness of the local industry, the inverse of τ .

Firms choose the talent level of the CEO to maximize profits, defined as the surplus generated in production, $s(x, a, d)$, net of the compensation paid to the CEO, $w(x)$. Therefore, the maximization problem that determines the talent hired by a type- a firm with export status d is

$$\max_x \{s(x, a, d) - w(x)\}. \quad (4)$$

Let $x(a)$ be the sorting function and $S \in (0, 1)$ be a fixed sharing rule. Then, the earnings at a firm with productivity a and export status d can be expressed by¹⁵

$$w(x(a), a, d) = S \left[(1 + d\tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{r(x(a), a, 0)}{\sigma} - v(1 + f + d\kappa) \right] + v. \quad (5)$$

We observe in Eq. (5) that earnings at both exporting and non-exporting firms depend positively on the revenues raised from domestic sales. However, CEOs in exporting firms earn additional earnings that originate from foreign sales, which depend on the level of trade cost τ . Then, trade openness (that is, a fall in τ) could impact earnings operating through two channels. First, through an impact on domestic revenues, that is, a fall or rise in $r(x(a), a, 0)$, which is relevant to both exporting and non-exporting firms. Second, through a direct reduction in the trade costs from serving foreign markets, that is, a fall in τ , which is only relevant for exporting firms.

¹⁵The derivation of the equilibrium earnings equation is provided in Appendix B.

3.3 Parametrization

Talent to run a firm has a continuous distribution function $t(x) = x^{-\gamma}$ with $\gamma \geq 2$, over a support $(1, \infty)$. The firm's productivity is drawn from a distribution function $z(a) = a^{-\theta}$ with $\theta \geq 2$, over a support $(1, \infty)$. In addition, let $c(x, a)^{1-\sigma} = x^\beta a^\alpha$. Then, the revenue function $r(x, a, 0)$ is supermodular in (x, a) , which is sufficient to have positive sorting $x'(a) > 0$. Thus, the sorting function can be expressed as $x(a) = \lambda a^\mu$, where $\lambda > 0$ and $\mu > 0$.¹⁶

Thus, Eqs. (3) and (5) imply

$$w(x(a), a, d) = S \left[\left(1 + d\tau^{1-\sigma}\right) \frac{\phi a^\rho}{\sigma} - v(1 + f + d\kappa) \right] + v, \quad (6)$$

where ϕa^ρ is the parametrized expression for the domestic revenues; that is, $r(x(a), a, 0) = \phi a^\rho$ with $\phi > 0$ and $\rho > 0$.¹⁷

We next discuss two remarks, which refer to the existence of selection by firms in production and the export market (Remark 1) and to the impact of a fall in the trade cost on the selection thresholds (Remark 2). A discussion of these results is important to understand the main conclusions derived from the simulation exercise that we perform later. However, we present these results without a formal proof because they are directly implied by Melitz (2003). Hereafter, we denote by $a_{0,\tau}$ the lowest productivity level among all of the firms that produce in the domestic economy under trade policy τ , and by $a_{1,\tau}$ the lowest productivity level among the exporting firms. Assumption 1 ensures that $a_{0,\tau} < a_{1,\tau}$, which is sufficient to generate a partition of firms.

Assumption 1. $\kappa > \tau^{1-\sigma}(1 + f)$.

Remark 1. *Firms with productivity strictly lower than $a_{0,\tau}$ do not start production. Firms with a productivity level weakly greater than $a_{0,\tau}$ but strictly lower than $a_{1,\tau}$ start production, but only serve the domestic economy. Firms with productivity weakly greater than $a_{1,\tau}$ start production and serve the foreign market.*

¹⁶Sort top-down implies that in equilibrium $N \int_a^\infty m^{-\theta} dm = L \int_{x(a)}^\infty \eta^{-\gamma} d\eta$, where N is the mass of incumbent firms, and L is the total labor force. Then, solving the latter equation, we obtain that $x = \lambda a^\mu$, where $\lambda = \left(\frac{N(\gamma-1)}{L(\theta-1)}\right)^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}}$ and $\mu = \frac{1-\theta}{1-\gamma}$.

¹⁷We have denoted: $\phi = R \left[\frac{v}{P(\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma})} \right]^{1-\sigma} \lambda^\beta$ and $\rho = \alpha + \mu\beta$.

A direct implication of Remark 1 is that exporting firms exhibit a higher total factor productivity than non-exporting firms. We now state the consequences of a fall in policy parameter τ on the productive thresholds $a_{0,\tau}$ and $a_{1,\tau}$.

Remark 2. *Trade openness increases the equilibrium productivity threshold for producing firms; that is, $a_{0,\tau'} > a_{0,\tau}$ for $\tau' < \tau$. Trade openness decreases the equilibrium productivity threshold for exporting firms; that is, $a_{1,\tau'} < a_{1,\tau}$ for $\tau' < \tau$.*

The type of selection described in Remark 1 implies a positive correlation between a firm's productivity and a firm's export orientation. In addition, the parametrized expression for domestic revenues show that the most productive firms accrue more revenues than the least productive ones. Lastly, Eq. (6) shows that CEO pay is higher in more productive firms. Hence, in the model, more productive firms are more export oriented, generate greater revenues, and pay higher CEO compensation. The latter is the same relationship that we observe in the data between the firm's productivity, export orientation, revenues, and CEO pay (see Table 2).

We conclude this subsection by presenting the equilibrium earnings equation in an alternative way. In Appendix C, we prove that $\phi = \sigma w(1+f)a_{0,\tau}^{-\rho}$ and we also derive a closed solution for the thresholds $a_{0,\tau}$ and $a_{1,\tau}$.¹⁸ Then, we can express domestic revenues as:

$$r(x(a), a, 0) = \sigma v(1+f) \left(\frac{a}{a_{0,\tau}} \right)^\rho, \quad (7)$$

and the equilibrium earnings equation as:

$$w(x(a), a, d) = S \left[(1 + d\tau^{1-\sigma}) v(1+f) \left(\frac{a}{a_{0,\tau}} \right)^\rho - v(1+f + d\kappa) \right] + v. \quad (8)$$

Notice that Eq. (8) depends exclusively on the production threshold $a_{0,\tau}$, but not on any of the aggregate variables of the model. Hence, aggregation of the model is not necessary to perform a comparative statics on the earnings equation. Eq. (8) is the main object of our analysis. In the next section, we use this equation to simulate the effect of trade on CEO equilibrium pay across firms with different productivity, within a given industry. The latter simulation motivates the empirical analysis of Section 5.

¹⁸As a byproduct of the analysis of Appendix C, we also prove Remark 2 for the parametrized model.

3.4 Simulation

We now perform a simulation to illustrate the effect of a fall in the trade cost on CEO equilibrium pay across heterogeneous firms, within a given industry. We consider the case of an industry with 100,000 firms with productivities over the support $[1, 100]$. Our policy experiment entails a fall in the trade cost from $\tau = 2$ to $\tau' = 1.5$. Table 3 describes the parameter values used for this simulation.

Fig. 2 plots the changes in CEO equilibrium pay that result from the policy experiment. We observe three groups of firms. First, firms with productivity $a_{0,1.5} \leq a < a_{1,1.5}$.¹⁹ Those are the firms that, after the trade policy, continue exclusively serving the local industry. CEO pay falls at these firms; Remark 2 and Eqs. (7) and (8) explain why. A fall in the trade cost raises the production threshold a_0 (Remark 2). Hence, domestic revenues fall (Eq. 7), and thus, total revenues also fall for these firms, which only serve the domestic industry.²⁰ Then, rent sharing implies that the trade policy reduces CEO pay in firms with productivity $a_{0,1.5} \leq a < a_{1,1.5}$ (Eq. 8).²¹

Consider now the group of firms with a productivity level $a_{1,1.5} \leq a < a_{1,2}$. These firms only serve the local industry before the policy but become exporters once the policy is introduced. In these firms, domestic revenues fall, as it occurs in the first group of firms that we analyzed previously. However, new exporters receive additional revenues from their sales in the foreign market. The latter overcompensates for the fall in domestic revenues. Then, the effect of the trade policy on total revenues is positive for all the firms with productivity $a_{1,1.5} \leq a < a_{1,2}$. However, new exporters must pay an export entry cost. The export cost reduces profits, and by rent sharing, implies that some of the firms from this second group exhibit a fall in CEO pay whereas others experience a rise, as we observe in Fig. 2. More precisely, the change in CEO compensation in this second group of firms is equal to the change in total revenues, multiplied

¹⁹A number of producing firms will exit the market after the trade policy is introduced in the industry. These firms are those with productivity $a_{0,2} \leq a < a_{0,1.5}$. We focus the analysis only on firms that continue producing.

²⁰A fall in trade costs τ makes exporting firms incur smaller costs from selling their products offshore. Then, exporting firms expand their sales in foreign markets and the profits of these firms rise. There is also more entry as prospective firms respond to the higher potential returns associated with a good productivity draw. The increased labor demand by the more productive firms and the new entrants bids up real wage, which reduces the domestic revenues for every producing firm.

²¹We also observe in Fig. 2 that the fall in CEO pay is more pronounced for the most productive firms within this first group, which is directly implied by Eq. (8).

by the constant S/σ , and scaled down by Svk (see Eq. 5).

Lastly, consider the most productive firms. These are firms with a productivity level weakly greater than $a_{1,2}$. These firms were already exporters before the trade policy. In this case, the extra revenues derived from the lower cost of serving the foreign market overcompensates for the fall in domestic revenues. Moreover, these firms do not have to incur an incremental fixed cost to enter the export market. Consistently, we observe that the change in CEO pay is positive at these firms.

Overall, the model described in this section motivates an empirical analysis that assesses the impact of industry-level trade intensity on CEO pay at firms with different levels of productivity. The latter analysis would shed light on the distributional effect of trade on the CEO market. Note that we have also plotted a fitted regression line in Fig. 2, which is the simulated analogous to a regression for firm-level real data within an industry. Our empirical analysis aims to estimate the analogous regression for the one plotted in Fig. 2, but with real data.

4 Data

In this section, we describe the data and their sources. Our data comes from *Compustat*, which contains information on the historical financial records of US companies and the compensation of top executives at these firms. We merge the *Execucomp* file, the *Fundamentals Annual* file, and the *Segment* file of the *Compustat* dataset to assemble panel data of 1,085 companies spanning the period 1992-2017.²² Our panel contains information on both firm and top executive characteristics.²³

CEO data

The *Execucomp* file contains information for 8,115 executives who have been appointed CEO at some date during the period 1992-2017. Following Gabaix and Landier (2008), we use the TDC1 variable to build the CEO total compensation variable, which sums up salary, bonuses, the total

²²Our panel is unbalanced, and thus, the information for some firms is not available for every year of the 1992-2017 period.

²³Our data cleaning process is as follows. *Compustat* contains information on 30,634 firms. Among those firms, 24,413 include information on sales and 4,193 also present data on foreign sales and the variables used to compute firm-level productivity. Lastly, 1,085 of the latter firms also contain information on CEO compensation.

value of restricted stocks granted, the Black-Scholes total value of stock options granted, and long-term incentive payouts. We deflate this variable using the US Consumer Price Index.

We also use *Execucomp* to retrieve information on CEO gender, age, degree earned, and the within-firm executive pay ranking. In addition, we identify whether the CEO is also the chairman of the company and if she/he is on the board of directors. We also extract information regarding the number of directors at each company and if an executive is listed in the Compensation Committee Interlocks and Insider Participation. Lastly, we use the information provided by this file to build two CEO tenure measures. The first measure is the number of years that the CEO has worked in the current firm (tenure at the firm). The second measure is the number of years that the executive has been appointed as CEO at any firm (tenure as CEO).

Firm data

We collect yearly information on the firms' characteristics from the *Fundamentals Annual* file during a period spanning 1950-2017. Concretely, we extract information using the Standard Industry Classification code at the four-digit level (SIC-4) on revenues, sales, number of employees, capital expenditure, capital stock net of depreciation,²⁴ cost of intermediate inputs, and R&D expenditure. We deflate revenues, sales, capital stock, and the cost of intermediate inputs using the US-GDP deflator index. We use this information to characterize the firms and also to compute a firm-level total factor productivity variable. For the latter, we rely on the approach developed by Levinsohn and Petrin (2003). We then kept the 1992-2017 period data and merged it with the CEO data. We exclude outliers that exhibit productivity levels significantly larger than the rest.²⁵

Trade openness

Our third set of data comes from the *Segment* file. We use this source to retrieve information on company annual export sales, which is identified as *salexg* in the *Segment* data file, for the

²⁴Information is disaggregated by buildings, construction in progress, land and improvements, leases, machinery and equipment, natural resources, and other plants and equipment.

²⁵Most of the productivity observations lie within seven standard deviations of the productivity distribution. Thus, we drop productivity observations which are larger than seven standard deviations. The deleted observations correspond to 17 observations for 7 firms in the database that is used to perform the regressions described in the next section.

1976-2017 period. For a firm i with a missing observation on export sales for a given year, we assign a value of zero to this observation if some firms operating in the same industry as firm i exported in some year during the period 1976-2017. Otherwise, we treat the latter observation as a missing value.²⁶ We build a trade openness variable at the industry-level as the weighted average of the firm-level ratio of export sales to total sales. We use the SIC-4 to circumscribe the industry, and the industry average is weighted by the firms' total sales. As we did beforehand, we keep the data corresponding to the period 1992-2017 and merge it with the two datasets described previously.

Tariffs

We merge the previous data with information on tariffs for the United States and the rest of the world. Data on tariffs was extracted from the World Integrated Trade Solution (WITS). We use tariffs to build the set of instrumental variables used in our empirical model.²⁷ Specifically, we consider the tariff rate charged for US imports at the SIC-4 level, *US tariffs*, and the tariff rate charged for US exports at the SIC-4 level, *world tariffs*.

5 Empirical strategy

The model presented in Section 3 shows that, within an industry, the effect of industry trade exposure on CEO pay depends on the productivity level of the firm. Specifically, Fig. 2 shows that industry openness increases CEO compensation in firms with productivity above a certain threshold, but decreases it in firms with productivity below the threshold. We test this prediction by using the following reduced-form model:

$$\ln w_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln o_{jt-1} + \alpha_2 \ln a_{it-1} + \alpha_3 (\ln o_{jt-1} \times \ln a_{it-1}) + X'_{it} \rho + \gamma_j + \delta_t + u_{it}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where w_{it} is CEO total compensation in firm i at time t , o_{jt-1} is equal to one plus industry j 's openness degree at time $t - 1$, a_{it-1} is firm i 's total factor productivity at time $t - 1$, X_{it} is a vector of firm-level covariates, γ_j are industry-fixed effects, δ_t are time-fixed effects, and u_{it} is

²⁶We circumscribe the industry at the SIC-4 level.

²⁷We discuss the potential endogeneity of our regressors of interest in the next section.

an i.i.d. error term.²⁸

Model (S2) is our baseline model. We include the first lag of the openness and productivity variables as a first way to address a potential problem of mutual causality.²⁹ In addition, we include a battery of covariates to control for potential confounding explanations of the CEO pay dispersion within industries. We rely on the literature on the determinants of CEO pay to select four sets of covariates.

First, as noted by Frydman (2019) and Edmans et al. (2017), the personal characteristics of CEOs may be an important determinant of their compensation. Therefore, a first group of covariates describes the CEO's characteristics. Specifically, we include age, gender, tenure at the firm, tenure as CEO, a dummy equal to one if she/he holds a doctoral degree, and a dummy equal to one if she/he belongs to the top five highest paid executives in the firm. We name this first set of covariates *CEO characteristics*.

In addition, as argued by Bertrand and Mullainathan (2001) and Bebchuk et al. (2002), rent extraction may be a source of the differences in CEO compensation across firms. Therefore, our second set of covariates intends to capture firm-level factors that drive rent extraction by CEOs. Concretely, we include the firm's number of board members, number of board member interlocks, a dummy equal to one if the CEO is also the chairman of the firm, and a dummy equal to one if the CEO is also a member of the board of directors. We name this second set of covariates *rent extraction*.

Third, a strand of literature, including Garicano and Rossi-Hansberg (2006), argues that manager compensation might be driven by the knowledge content of production workers. Consistent with the conclusions of these studies, we also include an R&D intensity variable as covariate. This variable is proxied by the firm's ratio of R&D expenditure over the summation of capital expenditure and R&D expenditure. We name this variable *organizational knowledge*.

Lastly, Gabaix and Landier (2008) posit that CEO compensation depends on the size of the firm. In our model, trade openness affects CEO compensation through the reallocation of revenues, such that more openness increases the size of revenues of more productive firms and then pushes CEO compensation up in these firms. To capture other factors besides the

²⁸Section 4 described the construction of the variables included in model S2.

²⁹We later estimate an instrumental variables model.

revenues' size effect, we include the firm's number of employees as our last set of covariates. We name this variable *size*.

We use model (S2) to test $\alpha_1 < 0$ and $\alpha_3 > 0$, which implies a negative effect of industry openness on CEO pay in the least productive firms, but a positive effect in the most productive ones (see Fig. 2).

5.1 Instrumental variables approach

As explained in Section 4, our industry openness variable is built as the weighted average of the firm-level ratio of export sales to total sales, for each industry. However, the number of firms with information on export sales is heterogeneous across industries. In some industries only 5% of the firms report export sales, whereas in others 80% do. Thus, changes in individual firms may have a non-trivial impact on the openness variable and create a mechanical correlation with the outcome. Moreover, the openness of the industry may be driven by the behavior of a few large firms (the openness measure weights by firm size), driving a reverse causality problem.³⁰ Firm's productivity may also be endogenous due to reverse causality with the outcome, or to the existence of unobservables correlated with both productivity and CEO pay. For instance, changes in the compensation incentive scheme may impact both CEO pay and the firm's productivity.

Lagged models, like (S2), are not always a convincing method to address endogeneity problems. The use of lagged regressors forces a loss of contemporaneous variance, which may be relevant, and might drive inconsistent estimates and invalid hypothesis testing (Reed, 2015). Then, we estimate a second model that relies on the use of instrumental variables. We include *US tariffs* and *world tariffs*, defined in Section 4, and the first lag of the endogenous regressors (openness, productivity, and the interaction between openness and productivity) in the set of instruments.

Tariffs, by definition, are strongly correlated with industry openness. Furthermore, a change in tariffs impacts the incentives for firms to absorb overseas new technologies (Parente and Prescott, 2000), or to allocate resources efficiently within the firm (Bond et al., 2013).

³⁰The inclusion of industry fixed effects allows us to control for the time-invariant omitted characteristics of the industry that are correlated with both industry openness and the outcome.

The latter generates a correlation between tariffs and firms' total factor productivity. However, tariffs are determined by governments, and thus, are exogenous to the firm. Hence, we assume that tariffs are uncorrelated with any unobserved component of CEO pay, and any correlation with the outcome is triggered solely through its correlation with industry openness and the firm's total factor productivity.³¹ Therefore, we exploit tariff shocks as instruments for our endogenous regressors. We perform the following regression in the first stage:

$$y_{st} = Z'_{st}\phi + X'_{it}\theta + \gamma_j + \delta_t + \epsilon_{it},$$

for $y_{st} \in \{\ln o_{jt}, \ln a_{it}, \ln o_{jt} \times \ln a_{it}\}$, where Z_{st} is the vector of instruments,³² and ϵ_{it} is an i.i.d. error term.

Then, we obtain the predicted values $\widehat{\ln o_{jt}}$, $\widehat{\ln a_{it}}$ and $(\widehat{\ln o_{jt} \times \ln a_{it}})$, and perform the second stage regression:

$$\ln w_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \widehat{\ln o_{jt}} + \beta_2 \widehat{\ln a_{it}} + \beta_3 (\widehat{\ln o_{jt} \times \ln a_{it}}) + X'_{it}\zeta + \gamma_j + \delta_t + v_{it}. \quad (\text{S3})$$

We assess the instruments' relevance by performing a Fisher test on the coefficients' regressors included in Z_{st} and check if the Staiger and Stock (1997) condition of relevance holds. We then perform a Hansen J-test to check the validity of over-identifying restrictions. We use model (S3) to test $\beta_1 < 0$ and $\beta_3 > 0$. Section 6 presents the estimates of our baseline model (S2) and our preferred model (S3).

5.2 Distributional effects

We build the marginal effect of trade openness on CEO compensation as

$\partial \ln w^{CEO} / \partial \ln o = \beta_1 + \beta_3 \ln a$.³³ The model in Section 3 predicts $\beta_1 < 0$ and $\beta_3 > 0$, and the existence of a threshold firm with productivity $\ln a^* = -\beta_1/\beta_3$; that is, a negative marginal effect

³¹Our data match with 109 different SIC-4 industries containing information on both *US tariffs* and *world tariffs* for the period 1992-2017. Moreover, all of these industries exhibit variation over time in the *world tariffs* variable, whereas 99% of them exhibit variation in the *US tariffs* variable. Therefore, the heterogeneous and exogenous nature of tariffs allow us to exploit tariff shocks as instruments for our endogenous regressors.

³²Recall that the set of instruments include: *US tariffs*, *world tariffs*, and the first lag of the corresponding dependent variable (y_{st-1}),

³³The computation of the marginal effects for model (S2) is analogous.

for firms with productivity $a < a^*$, but a positive marginal effect for firms with productivity $a > a^*$.

In addition, we estimate the aggregate effect of trade openness on the CEO's equilibrium compensation, or *aggregate elasticity*, as follows:

$$\text{Aggregate elasticity} = \frac{\sum_i \sum_t (\beta_1 + \beta_3 \ln a_{it}) w_{it}}{\sum_i \sum_t w_{it}},$$

where the nominator is the aggregate change of CEO compensation when trade openness level increases by 1%, and the denominator is the aggregate level of CEO compensation. Hence, the aggregate elasticity measures the total percentage change in CEO compensation as a result of an increase of 1% in the trade openness measure. The computation of the aggregate elasticity will reveal if, despite the distributional consequences of trade exposure on the CEO market, the overall effect of trade openness on CEO pay is still positive.

6 Results

We present and discuss our empirical results in this section. Table 4 shows the estimates of model (S2), the baseline model. Column (1) considers only industry and year fixed effects, whereas columns (2) through (5) expand this specification by including, separately, each set of covariates. Column (6) shows the result with the full set of covariates. We will focus on specification (6) since the results are roughly similar across columns (1) through (6).

We observe a negative effect of openness on CEO compensation, and a positive interaction effect. Therefore, within an industry, greater trade exposure raises CEO compensation in firms with productivity above a certain threshold but reduces it at the firms with productivity below the threshold. In this case, the threshold firm is at the 51st percentile of the productivity distribution. We also present an F -test to evaluate the joint significance of the coefficients of openness, productivity, and the interaction between them. The F -statistic is equal to 34.12, and thus, our model is statistically significant.

In addition, we present in Table 4 the marginal effect of openness on CEO compensation, that is, $\partial \ln w / \partial \ln o = \alpha_1 + \alpha_3 \ln a$, in firms at the 99th, 95th, 25th and 20th percentiles of the

productivity distribution. The marginal effect is equal to 3.15 and 1.75 in firms at the 99th and 95th percentiles, respectively. Then, an increase of 10% in the industry openness degree (for instance, from 0.5 to 0.55) raises CEO compensation by 31.5% and 17.5% in these firms, respectively. In the case of firms at the 25th and 20th percentiles, the marginal effect is -0.32 and -0.39 , respectively. Hence, contrary to what is observed for the most productive firms, CEO compensation falls with trade exposure in firms at the lower percentiles of the productivity distribution. The aggregate elasticity implied by our estimates is 0.17. That means that, despite the distributional consequences of trade exposure on the market for CEOs, the overall effect of trade openness on CEO pay is positive.

We next plot the firms' productivity levels against the firms' predicted marginal effect of openness on CEO pay, which is measured by $\hat{\alpha}_1 + \hat{\alpha}_3 \ln a$. We do so for the specification of column (6) of Table 4. Fig. 3a exhibits the result. We observe that the marginal effect of trade openness on CEO pay is negative for the group of firms with productivity below the threshold (51st percentile). On the contrary, the trade effect is positive for firms above the threshold. Furthermore, the marginal effect is monotonically increasing with productivity. Overall, the pattern plotted in Fig. 3a is consistent with the simulation provided by Fig. 2.

Table 5 shows the results of the instrumental variables model (S3). Columns (1) through (6) are analogous to those discussed in Table 4. Column (6), the specification that includes the full set of covariates, confirms the results derived from the baseline model (S2). In this case, the threshold firm is at the 60th percentile. The effect of trade openness on CEO pay is negative in firms with productivity below the threshold, whereas it is positive in firms above the threshold. Specifically, the marginal effect of trade openness on CEO compensation is 3.42 and 2.01 in firms at the 99th and 95th percentiles, respectively, and it is -0.60 and -0.70 in those at the 25th and 20th percentiles, respectively. The F -test for the joint significance of the openness, productivity, and interaction coefficients confirms the statistical significance of the model. In addition, we find an aggregate elasticity of 0.09. Lastly, Fig. 3b confirms the positive relation between productivity and the predicted marginal effect of openness.

Table 5 also reports the tests for the validity of the instruments. In all specifications, the F -statistics in the first stage regression for openness, productivity, and the interaction satisfy the Staiger and Stock (1997) condition for relevance of the instruments. In addition, the Hansen

J-test fails to reject the null hypothesis that the over-identifying restrictions are valid.

We conclude by studying the within-sample explanatory power of trade openness on CEO pay that is implied by the marginal effects computed in Table 5. To do so, we first denote by ex_{it} the exports of firm i at time t . We then compute the within-sample change of trade openness in industry j during the period 1992-2017 as $\left(\frac{\sum_{i \in j} ex_{i,2017}}{\sum_{i \in j} s_{i,2017}}\right) / \left(\frac{\sum_{i \in j} ex_{i,1992}}{\sum_{i \in j} s_{i,1992}}\right) - 1$, where i denotes firms, j denotes industries, and s_i is the firm's total sales. We also compute the within-sample change of CEO compensation in firm i during 1992-2017 as $(w_{i,2017}/w_{i,1992}) - 1$. Then, we calculate each firm's average productivity during the period 1992-2017 and, with that computation, we identify the percentiles of each firm. Lastly, we multiply the within-sample change in trade openness by the marginal effects computed in Table 5 to quantify the explanatory power of trade openness for the within-sample change in CEO pay at four points of the productivity distribution. We get that trade openness explains 34%, 20%, 8%, and 47% of the observed increase in CEO pay during the period 1992-2017 in firms at the 99th, 95th, 25th, and 20th percentiles of the productivity distribution, respectively.³⁴

Discussion

Our results show that trade openness increases CEO pay at the top of the distribution but decreases it at the bottom of the distribution.³⁵ We conclude this paper by discussing how the latter distributional effect in the CEO market may impact the top of the income distribution.

Consider two percentiles of the income distribution, h and l . Let g be the ratio of the average income of agents at percentile h relative to the average income of those at percentile l . Suppose that each percentile $i \in \{h, l\}$ is composed by N_c top executives and N_n other agents, with an average income of y_c^i and y_n^i , respectively. Then,

$$g \approx \frac{N_c y_c^h + N_n y_n^h}{N_c y_c^l + N_n y_n^l}.$$

Let $\epsilon_{g,o}$ be the overall percentage change in g when trade openness increases by 1%. Fixing

³⁴As a reference, we present, in Appendix D, the estimates of a model that include the contemporaneous values of the openness and productivity variables, instead of the first lag of them.

³⁵*Compustat* covers Standard & Poor's companies. Therefore, CEOs at the bottom of the distribution indeed belong to the top of the US earnings distribution. The CEO at the 25th percentile of the *Compustat* earnings distribution receives an annual compensation of about US\$ 1.3 million. As a reference, data from WDI show that the annual average income of the top 1% of the US income distribution is about US\$ 1.2 million.

N_c and N_n , we get the following expression for $\epsilon_{g,o}$:

$$\epsilon_{g,o} \approx \mu_c^h \varepsilon_{y_c^h,o} - \mu_c^l \varepsilon_{y_c^l,o} + (1 - \mu_c^h) \varepsilon_{y_n^h,o} - (1 - \mu_c^l) \varepsilon_{y_n^l,o}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mu_c^i = \frac{N_c y_c^i}{N_c y_c^i + N_n y_n^i}$ for $i \in \{h, l\}$.

Eq. (9) provides a direct link between the marginal effect of openness on CEO compensation and the aggregate impact of trade on inequality at the top of the income distribution. The proportion of the aggregate elasticity, $\epsilon_{g,o}$, that is accounted for by the marginal effect of openness on CEO compensation, $\varepsilon_{y_c^h,o}$ and $\varepsilon_{y_c^l,o}$, can be then computed as:

$$E = \frac{\mu_c^h \varepsilon_{y_c^h,o} - \mu_c^l \varepsilon_{y_c^l,o}}{\epsilon_{g,o}}.$$

We now provide an example of how distributional effects in the CEO market may explain a fraction of the overall impact of trade on top income inequality. Let $h = 99.999$ and $l = 99$. Bakija et al. (2008) document that executives, managers and supervisors in the non-finance sector account for approximately 40% of those at the top 0.1% in terms of income in the 1979-2005 period. Hence, we can roughly assume that $\mu_c^h = \mu_c^l = 0.4$. From Table 5, we assume that $\varepsilon_{y_c^h,o} = 2.7$ (the average of the marginal effect of openness on CEO compensation at the highest percentiles) and $\varepsilon_{y_c^l,o} = -0.65$ (the average of the marginal effect of openness on CEO compensation at the lowest percentiles). Then, using WID and WDI data for the period 1975-2018, we compute the US correlation between the log of g and the log of trade openness, which is 1.7; then, we consider $\epsilon_{g,o} = 1.7$. This implies that $E \approx 0.79$. Therefore, in this example, 79% of the overall effect of trade on inequality at the top of the distribution is accounted for by the distributional effects in the CEO market.

7 Conclusions

This paper analyzed the distributional effects of trade openness on the market for CEOs. We use a general equilibrium open-economy model with heterogeneous firms and heterogenous CEO talent to motivate our empirical analysis. The model shows that a fall in trade costs

raises CEO pay in the most productive firms but reduces it in the least productive ones. A trade-induced reallocation of revenues across firms is the relevant channel through which the effects are triggered in the model.

We used US firm-level data to test the main prediction of the model. We found that an increase of 10% in the industry openness degree raises CEO compensation by about 35% and 20% in firms at the 99th and 95th percentiles of the productivity distribution, respectively. However, this rise in trade reduces CEO compensation by 7% in firms at the 20th percentile. We refer to the latter as the distributional effect of trade openness on the market for CEOs. We also find that the aggregate elasticity implied by our estimates is about 0.1, meaning that an increase of 10% in trade openness raises aggregate CEO compensation by 1%. Overall, our findings show that trade openness impacts inequality within a group that is representative of the very top of the income distribution.

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Figures

Figure 1: US CEO Pay Dispersion (90th/25th ratio)

Source: Frydman and Saks (2010).

Figure 2: Effect of the Trade Policy on CEO Pay

Figure 3: Marginal Effect of Openness on CEO Compensation

Note: Panel (a) for model (S2), and panel (b) for model (S3).

Tables

Table 1: Trade Openness and Top Income Inequality

	(1)	(2)	(3)
	$z^{0.001/0.01}$	$z^{0.001/0.1}$	$z^{0.001/1}$
Ln trade to GDP	0.1026** (0.0413)	0.2146** (0.0838)	0.3433*** (0.1260)
Govt. size	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes
Countries	59	59	59
Observations	1,637	1,637	1,637

Note: (a) Robust standard errors in parentheses. (b) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

Table 2: Exports, Revenues, CEO Compensation, and Productivity

A. Ln (1+exports)	
Ln productivity	0.0104*** (0.0025)
Industry fixed effects	Yes
B. Ln revenues	
Ln productivity	0.1146*** (0.0049)
Industry fixed effects	Yes
C. Ln CEO compensation	
Ln productivity	0.0300*** (0.0024)
Industry fixed effects	Yes

Note: (a) Obs. in panel A = 49,366; Obs. in panel B = 185,315 ; Obs. in panel C = 41,006. (b) Clustered standard errors in parentheses. (c) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

Table 3: Parameter Values

Parameter	Description	Value
τ	Trade cost (before)	2
τ'	Trade cost (after)	1.5
e	Industry entry cost	1
κ	Export entry cost	8
f	Fixed production cost	2
w	Production worker wage	1
σ	Elasticity of substitution	2
θ	Curvature of the productivity distribution	2.5
γ	Curvature of the CEO talent distribution	7
β	Cost function parameter related to talent	0.5
α	Cost function parameter related to productivity	0.5
ζ	Probability of a bad shock	0.1

Table 4: Effect of Openness on Compensation, Lagged Model (S2)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Openness	-1.6286** (0.6801)	-1.5450** (0.6631)	-1.6675** (0.6762)	-1.6983** (0.6843)	-1.5338** (0.6344)	-1.5853** (0.6265)
Productivity	0.0266** (0.0026)	0.0255** (0.0026)	0.0261** (0.0026)	0.0267** (0.0026)	0.0242** (0.0025)	0.0232** (0.0024)
Interaction	0.0655** (0.0251)	0.0623** (0.0248)	0.0670** (0.0251)	0.0677** (0.0251)	0.0617** (0.0232)	0.0623** (0.0231)
F-statistic	40.32 [0.0000]	37.99 [0.0000]	39.60 [0.0000]	41.04 [0.0000]	34.89 [0.0000]	34.12 [0.0000]
Threshold firm percentile	0.48	0.48	0.48	0.49	0.49	0.51
Marginal effect percentile 0.99	3.36	3.19	3.43	3.45	3.14	3.15
Marginal effect percentile 0.95	1.88	1.79	1.92	1.93	1.75	1.75
Marginal effect percentile 0.25	-0.30	-0.28	-0.31	-0.33	-0.30	-0.32
Marginal effect percentile 0.20	-0.38	-0.35	-0.39	-0.40	-0.37	-0.39
Aggregate elasticity	0.19	0.18	0.19	0.19	0.17	0.17
Industry effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CEO characteristics	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Rent extraction	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Organizational knowledge	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Size	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Observations	27,560	27,560	27,560	27,560	27,560	27,560

Note: (a) Clustered standard errors in parentheses. (b) P-values in brackets. (c) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

Table 5: Effect of Openness on Compensation, Instrumental Variables Model (S3)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Openness	-4.1021*** (1.1438)	-3.8314*** (1.0728)	-4.0483*** (1.1346)	-4.2405*** (1.1485)	-2.5396** (1.2406)	-2.4868** (1.1719)
Productivity	0.0303*** (0.0049)	0.0286*** (0.0048)	0.0299*** (0.0050)	0.0305*** (0.0049)	0.0250*** (0.0046)	0.0238*** (0.0045)
Interaction	0.1421*** (0.0429)	0.1373*** (0.0392)	0.1436*** (0.0426)	0.1461*** (0.0429)	0.0844* (0.0465)	0.0893** (0.0428)
F-statistic 2nd stage	22.02	16.79	19.31	21.29	16.68	12.07
Model significance	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]
Threshold firm percentile	0.64	0.61	0.62	0.64	0.68	0.60
Marginal effect percentile 0.99	5.32	5.23	5.47	5.40	3.06	3.42
Marginal effect percentile 0.95	3.03	3.05	3.16	3.08	1.71	2.01
Marginal effect percentile 0.25	-1.10	-0.93	-1.01	-1.14	-0.76	-0.60
Marginal effect percentile 0.20	-1.25	-1.08	-1.17	-1.30	-0.85	-0.70
Aggregate elasticity	0.12	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.06	0.09
Openness F-statistic	68.64	69.38	69.14	68.65	68.57	69.80
1st stage	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]
Productivity F-statistic	1,009.74	899.49	999.89	957.80	655.23	571.08
1st stage	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]
Interaction F-statistic	75.81	75.50	75.26	76.06	68.20	67.77
1st stage	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]	[0.0000]
J-statistic (Hansen test)	1.24	1.36	1.33	1.74	3.18	2.62
	[0.5379]	[0.5060]	[0.5138]	[0.4185]	[0.2036]	[0.2701]
Industry effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CEO characteristics	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Rent extraction	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Organizational knowledge	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Size	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Observations	9,995	9,995	9,995	9,995	9,995	9,995

Note: (a) Clustered standard errors in parentheses. (b) P-values in brackets. (c) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

Appendices

Appendix A: surplus equation

The consumer's maximization problem is described by

$$\max_{q(\psi)} U \quad \text{subject to} \quad R = \int_{\psi \in \Psi} p(\psi)q(\psi)d\psi,$$

where $R = PQ = \int_{\psi \in \Psi} r(\psi)d\psi$ denotes aggregate expenditure, $U \equiv Q$, and $P = \left(\int_{\psi \in \Psi} p(\psi)^{1-\sigma} d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma}}$ is an index of all the varieties' prices.

We can get the optimal consumption for individual varieties:

$$q(\psi) = Q \left[\frac{p(\psi)}{P} \right]^{-\sigma}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

Let $p(x, a)$ be the pricing rule set for sales in the domestic market in a type- a firm that is managed by a type- x CEO. Firms optimally choose $p(x, a)$ to maximize the surplus earned from domestic sales. Therefore, the pricing rule $p(x, a)$ solves

$$\max_{p(x,a)} \{p(x, a)q(x, a) - vc(x, a)q(x, a)\}.$$

Analogously, the pricing rule for foreign sales, $p_{ex}(x, a)$, solves

$$\max_{p_{ex}(x,a)} \{p_{ex}(x, a)q(x, a) - v\tau c(x, a)q(x, a)\}.$$

Using the demand function (A1), we get:

$$p(x, a) = \frac{vc(a, x)}{\left(\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}\right)}, \quad (\text{A2})$$

Hence, denoting by $p(x, a, d)$ the pricing rule set by a firm with export status d , we obtain

$$p(x, a, 0) = p(x, a), \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$p(x, a, 1) = \begin{cases} p(x, a), & \text{in the domestic market} \\ \tau p(x, a), & \text{in foreign markets,} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A4})$$

We can now use the pricing rule (A4) to obtain

$$r(x, a, 0) = R \left[\frac{v}{P\left(\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}\right)} \right]^{1-\sigma} c(x, a)^{1-\sigma}, \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$r(x, a, d) = (1 + d\tau^{1-\sigma})r(x, a, 0). \quad (\text{A6})$$

Let now $L(x, a, d)$ be the production cost (in terms of production workers) of a firm with export status d , and by $L_{ex}(x, a, 1)$ the extra production cost incurred by an exporting firm. A constant marginal cost across production levels implies that the demand for the labor of production workers (l) is a linear function of the output (q): $l = f + cq$. Then, the cost structure discussed in Section 3.1 implies that

$$L(x, a, 0) = v(c(x, a)q(x, a) + f), \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$L_{ex}(x, a, 1) = v(\tau c(x, a)q(x, a) + \kappa). \quad (\text{A8})$$

Hence, using (A1), the pricing rule (A4), and (A5) we obtain

$$L(x, a, 0) = \left(\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma} \right) r(x, a, 0) + vf, \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$L_{ex}(x, a, 1) = \tau^{1-\sigma} \left(\frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma} \right) r(x, a, 0) + v\kappa. \quad (\text{A10})$$

In addition, we denote by $s(x, a, 0) = r(x, a, 0) - L(x, a, 0)$ the surplus generated from domestic sales, by $r_{ex}(x, a, 1) = \tau^{1-\sigma}r(x, a, 0)$ the revenues earned from export sales, and by $s_{ex}(x, a, 1) = r_{ex}(x, a, 1) - L_{ex}(x, a, 1)$ the extra surplus generated by an exporting firm. Then, the surplus produced by a firm with export status d is

$$s(x, a, d) = r(x, a, 0) - L(x, a, 0) + d[r_{ex}(x, a, 1) - L_{ex}(x, a, 1)]. \quad (\text{A11})$$

Therefore, using (A9), (A10), and the definition of $r_{ex}(x, a, 1)$, we can express the surplus of

non-exporting and exporting firms, respectively, as

$$s(x, a, 0) = \frac{r(x, a, 0)}{\sigma} - vf, \quad (\text{A12})$$

$$s(x, a, 1) = (1 + \tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{r(x, a, 0)}{\sigma} - v(f + \kappa). \quad (\text{A13})$$

Appendix B: equilibrium earnings equation

The first order condition of (4) is

$$w'(x) = \frac{\partial s(x, a(x), d)}{\partial x}, \quad (\text{B1})$$

where $a(x)$ is the productivity level of the firm that hires the CEO of talent x . Denote by x_0 the least talented CEO in producing firms and by x_1 the least talented CEO in exporting firms. Let $w(x, a(x), d)$ be the equilibrium value of $w(x)$. We can integrate the slope of the wage function (B1), with respect to x , to obtain a wage function $w(x, a(x), d)$ that describes the wages earned by CEOs with talent x working in exporting and non-exporting firms:

$$w(x, a(x), d) = \int_{x_d}^x \frac{\partial s(j, a(j), d)}{\partial j} dj + w(x_d, a(x_d), d). \quad (\text{B2})$$

In equilibrium, two continuation values for earnings must be satisfied:

$w(x_0, a(x_0), 0) = v$ and $w(x_1, a(x_1), 0) = w(x_1, a(x_1), 1)$. The first condition requires that the least talented CEO must be indifferent to working as a manager or as a production worker. The second condition imposes the continuation value over the wage of the least talented CEO in an exporting firm. Denoting by $S \in (0, 1)$ a fixed sharing rule, we get

$$w(x, a(x), 0) = S \left[\frac{r(x, a(x), 0)}{\sigma} - \frac{r(x_0, a(x_0), 0)}{\sigma} \right] + v, \quad (\text{B3})$$

$$w(x, a(x), 1) = S \left[(1 + \tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{r(x, a(x), 0)}{\sigma} - \tau^{1-\sigma} \frac{r(x_1, a(x_1), 0)}{\sigma} - \frac{r(x_0, a(x_0), 0)}{\sigma} \right] + v. \quad (\text{B4})$$

In addition, we define the profit of a type- a firm with exporting status d as $\pi(x, a(x), d) = s(x, a(x), d) - w(x, a(x), d)$. The continuation value for profit requires

$\pi(x_0, a(x_0), 0) = 0$ and $\pi(x_1, a(x_1), 0) = \pi(x_1, a(x_1), 1)$. The first condition requires that the profits of firms managed by the least talented CEO must be equal to the outside option, which is, by assumption, zero. The second condition requires that the profits of the marginal exporting firm must be equal to the profits that would have been obtained if that firm were to sell all of its production in the domestic market. Then

$$\frac{r(x_0, a(x_0), 0)}{\sigma} = v(1 + f), \quad (\text{B5})$$

$$\tau^{1-\sigma} \frac{r(x_1, a(x_1), 0)}{\sigma} = v\kappa. \quad (\text{B6})$$

By substituting (B5) and (B6) into wage equations (B3) and (B4), we can express the earnings and profits equations as

$$w(x, a(x), 0) = S \left[\frac{r(x, a(x), 0)}{\sigma} - w(1 + f) \right] + v, \quad (\text{B7})$$

$$w(x, a(x), 1) = S \left[(1 + \tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{r(x, a(x), 0)}{\sigma} - w(1 + f + \kappa) \right] + v. \quad (\text{B8})$$

Alternatively,

$$w(x(a), a, 0) = S \left[\frac{r(x(a), a, 0)}{\sigma} - w(1 + f) \right] + v, \quad (\text{B9})$$

$$w(x(a), a, 1) = S \left[(1 + \tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{r(x(a), a, 0)}{\sigma} - w(1 + f + \kappa) \right] + v. \quad (\text{B10})$$

Appendix C: threshold values

We define the profit of a type- a firm with exporting status d as

$\pi(x, a(x), d) = s(x, a(x), d) - w(x, a(x), d)$. In Appendix A, we show that

$$s(x, a, d) = (1 + d\tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{r(x, a, 0)}{\sigma} - v(f + d\kappa). \quad (\text{C1})$$

In Appendix B, we show that

$$w(x, a(x), 1) = S \left[(1 + d\tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{r(x, a(x), 0)}{\sigma} - w(1 + f + d\kappa) \right] + v. \quad (\text{C2})$$

Then, using the parametrized expression for domestic revenues, $r(x(a), a, 0) = \phi a^\rho$, we can express profits as

$$\pi(x(a), a, d) = (1 - S) \left[(1 + d\tau^{1-\sigma}) \frac{\phi a^\rho}{\sigma} - v(1 + f + d\kappa) \right]. \quad (\text{C3})$$

Let $\pi_{ex}(x(a), a, 1) = \pi(x(a), a, 1) - \pi(x(a), a, 0)$ be the profits earned by a type- a exporting firm from foreign sales. Then, equation (C3) implies that:

$$\pi(x(a), a, 0) = (1 - S) \left[\frac{\phi a^\rho}{\sigma} - v(1 + f) \right], \quad (\text{C4})$$

$$\pi_{ex}(x(a), a, 1) = (1 - S) \left[\frac{\tau^{1-\sigma} \phi a^\rho}{\sigma} - v\kappa \right]. \quad (\text{C5})$$

Remark 1 implies that, for a given policy τ , thresholds $a_{0,\tau}$ and $a_{1,\tau}$ are such that $a_{0,\tau} = \inf\{a : \pi(x(a), a, 0) \geq 0\}$ and $a_{1,\tau} = \inf\{a : \pi_{ex}(x(a), a, 1) \geq 0\}$. Hence,

$$a_{0,\tau} = \left[\frac{\sigma v(1 + f)}{\phi} \right]^{\frac{1}{\rho}}, \quad (\text{C6})$$

$$a_{1,\tau} = \left[\frac{\sigma v\kappa}{\tau^{1-\sigma} \phi} \right]^{\frac{1}{\rho}}. \quad (\text{C7})$$

Let V be the net expected value of entry. Conditional on entrance, the expected profits earned by a firm are $\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} (1 - \zeta)^t \bar{\pi} = \bar{\pi}/\zeta$, where $\bar{\pi}$ is the average profit level of a firm in the market. Moreover, the probability for a firm to start production is equal to $\int_{a_{0,\tau}}^{\infty} z(y) dy$. Then, the free entry condition $V = 0$ is equivalent to: $\bar{\pi} \int_{a_{0,\tau}}^{\infty} z(y) dy = \zeta ve$. Average profits can be defined as:

$$\bar{\pi} = \underbrace{\frac{\int_{a_{0,\tau}}^{\infty} \pi(x(y), y, 0) z(y) dy}{\int_{a_{0,\tau}}^{\infty} z(y) dy}}_{\bar{\pi}_d} + \underbrace{\frac{\int_{a_{1,\tau}}^{\infty} \pi_{ex}(x(y), y, 1) z(y) dy}{\int_{a_{1,\tau}}^{\infty} z(y) dy}}_{\bar{\pi}_{ex}} \underbrace{\left(\frac{\int_{a_{1,\tau}}^{\infty} z(y) dy}{\int_{a_{0,\tau}}^{\infty} z(y) dy} \right)}_{p_{ex}}. \quad (\text{C8})$$

That is, average profits equal the average profits accrued from domestic selling, $\bar{\pi}_d$, plus the additional profits accrued by exporting firms, $\bar{\pi}_{ex}$, times the probability of being an exporting firm, p_{ex} . At this stage, we must impose the technical Assumption C1, which is sufficient for the average profits to be bounded.

Assumption C1. $1 + \rho - \theta < 0$.

Then, using equations (C4) to (C8), we can derive an expression for the average profits as a function of the technology thresholds $a_{0,\tau}$ and $a_{1,\tau}$:

$$\bar{\pi}_d = (1 - S) \left(\frac{\rho}{\theta - 1 - \rho} \right) v(1 + f), \quad (\text{C9})$$

$$\bar{\pi}_{ex,\tau} = (1 - S) \left(\frac{\rho}{\theta - 1 - \rho} \right) v\kappa, \quad (\text{C10})$$

$$p_{ex} = \left(\frac{a_{0,\tau}}{a_{1,\tau}} \right)^{\theta-1}, \quad (\text{C11})$$

$$\bar{\pi} = (1 - S)v \left(\frac{\rho}{\theta - 1 - \rho} \right) \left[1 + f + \kappa \left(\frac{a_{0,\tau}}{a_{1,\tau}} \right)^{\theta-1} \right]. \quad (\text{C12})$$

Then, the free entry condition can be expressed as:

$$(1 - S)v \left(\frac{\rho}{\theta - 1 - \rho} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\theta - 1} \right) [(1 + f)a_{0,\tau}^{1-\theta} + \kappa a_{1,\tau}^{1-\theta}] = \zeta ve. \quad (\text{C13})$$

Moreover, the zero cut-off profit conditions described by equations (C6) and (C7) relate the selection thresholds as follows:

$$a_{1,\tau} = \left[\frac{\kappa}{\tau^{1-\sigma}(1 + f)} \right]^{\frac{1}{\rho}} a_{0,\tau}. \quad (\text{C14})$$

Equations (C13) and (C14) solve for the thresholds:

$$a_{0,\tau} = \left(1 + f + \tau^{\frac{(\sigma-1)(1-\theta)}{\rho}} \kappa^{\frac{1+\rho-\theta}{\rho}} (1 + f)^{\frac{\theta-1}{\rho}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\theta-1}} \Psi, \quad (\text{C15})$$

$$a_{1,\tau} = \left(\kappa + \tau^{\frac{(\sigma-1)(\theta-1)}{\rho}} \kappa^{\frac{\theta-1}{\rho}} (1 + f)^{\frac{1+\rho-\theta}{\rho}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\theta-1}} \Psi, \quad (\text{C16})$$

where $\Psi = \left(\frac{(1-S)v \left(\frac{\rho}{\theta-1-\rho} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\theta-1} \right)}{\zeta ve} \right)^{\frac{1}{\theta-1}}$.

Note that we can directly show that $\partial a_{0,\tau} / \partial \tau < 0$ and $\partial a_{1,\tau} / \partial \tau > 0$ (Remark 2).

Appendix D: additional material

Table D1: Effect of Openness on Compensation, not Lagged Model

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Productivity	0.0277*** (0.0029)	0.0264*** (0.0028)	0.0254*** (0.0027)	0.0260*** (0.0027)	0.0265*** (0.0028)	0.0241*** (0.0027)	0.0232*** (0.0025)
Openness	-1.6622** (0.7392)	-1.4256* (0.7563)	-1.3538* (0.7400)	-1.4497* (0.7449)	-1.4934* (0.7621)	-1.3715* (0.7069)	-1.3966** (0.6956)
Interaction	0.0631** (0.0281)	0.0611** (0.0282)	0.0577** (0.0279)	0.0625** (0.0280)	0.0632** (0.0283)	0.0581** (0.0262)	0.0583** (0.0260)
Model	35.30 [0.0000]	34.00 [0.0000]	32.30 [0.0000]	33.90 [0.0000]	34.96 [0.0000]	29.64 [0.0000]	29.96 [0.0000]
Threshold firm percentile	0.54	0.41	0.42	0.40	0.43	0.42	0.44
Marginal effect percentile 0.99	3.12	3.20	3.01	3.29	3.29	3.03	3.02
Marginal effect percentile 0.95	1.72	1.85	1.74	1.90	1.89	1.74	1.73
Marginal effect percentile 0.25	-0.38	-0.19	-0.19	-0.18	-0.22	-0.19	-0.22
Marginal effect percentile 0.20	-0.46	-0.26	-0.25	-0.26	-0.29	-0.26	-0.28
Aggregate elasticity	0.17	0.22	0.20	0.22	0.22	0.20	0.20
Industry effects	Yes						
Year effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CEO characteristics	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Rent extraction	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Organizational knowledge	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Size	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Observations	27,851	27,851	27,851	27,851	27,851	27,851	27,851

Note: (a) Clustered standard errors in parentheses. (b) P-values in brackets. (c) *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.